

EFFECT OF LUTEOLIN ON OVARIAN MORPHOLOGY IN MICE WITH POLYCYSTIC OVARY SYNDROME (PCOS)

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17342049>

Relevance: Polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) is a complex and multifactorial reproductive, endocrine and metabolic disorder with diverse clinical manifestations, covering a wide spectrum of symptoms from reproductive dysfunction to metabolic disturbances, which poses significant challenges to patients' quality of life and health. The etiology of PCOS remains unclear and involves a complex interaction of genetics, environment and endocrine system. This makes prevention, early diagnosis and effective treatment particularly challenging. Current treatment strategies for PCOS are primarily aimed at symptomatic treatment rather than at curing the disease itself. Although existing medications such as oral contraceptives and insulin sensitizers can alleviate symptoms to some extent, their long-term use may be associated with a number of side effects such as lipid metabolism disorders and increased insulin resistance, and some patients may have a suboptimal response to therapy. Luteolin can regulate aromatase expression through the MKK3/6-p38 MAPK-CREB pathway. This study reveals a potential role for TPL2 as a novel target in estrogen biosynthesis, providing new insights for the treatment of PCOS.

Purpose of the study: to study of effect of luteolin on ovarian morphology in mice with PCOS.

Materials and methods: The experiments were performed in accordance with the good laboratory practice guidelines approved by Chengdu Institute of Biology, Chinese Academy of Sciences. All experimental procedures and animal collection were carried out under the license (CIBDWLL2023021) approved by the Animal Experimentation Committee of Chengdu Institute of Biology, Chinese Academy of Sciences. Female C57BL/6J mice were used to establish a polycystic ovary model. Female C57BL/6J mice were subcutaneously injected daily with 60 mg/kg dehydroepiandrosterone (DHEA) dissolved in 0.01 ml 95% ethanol and mixed with 0.09 ml olive oil. Then, the mice were fed with a high-fat diet. The control group was injected with 0.01 ml 95% ethanol and 0.09 ml olive oil and fed with a normal diet. One month after the model establishment, the reproductive and metabolic function were assessed to determine the success of the model. (Animals were maintained under standard conditions: free access to food and autoclaved water, controlled temperature of 22 °C, relative humidity of 45–55%, and a photoperiod of 12 h light and 12 h dark. They were weighed three times a week during the experimental period.). To determine the estrous cycle in mice, the estrous cycle was determined from 10:00 to 11:00 every day for 14 consecutive days.

Results: To examine the morphological changes of the ovaries, ovarian sections were stained with hematoxylin and eosin (H&E). In the ovaries of normal mice, follicles, mature oocytes, and corpora lutea were clearly visible. Histological analysis of the ovaries of PCOS mice revealed the development of follicular cysts characterized by thickening of the follicle walls, reduced granulosa cell layer, insufficient follicular reserve, and absence of corpora lutea. Compared with the PCOS group, luteolin and letrozole treatment significantly increased the number of primary follicles and decreased the number of cystic follicles. Normal ovarian morphology was observed in the experimental groups, but no ovarian cysts were observed.

Conclusions: Given the complexity of PCOS and the limitations of existing treatments, the development of new therapeutic agents is of critical importance. Research and development of new drugs will deepen the medical community's understanding of the causes and pathogenesis of PCOS, providing new ideas and methods for future research and treatment for PCOS patients.

The compounds studied in both sections demonstrated significant efficacy in alleviating the symptoms of PCOS. The results indicate that luteolin can alleviate the symptoms of PCOS in mice, improve the morphology of polycystic ovaries, restore normal morphology of ovaries at all stages of development, and stimulate ovulation.